

Delphi Survey Questionnaire

December 2022

RRIZSCALE

RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH & INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS AT REGIONAL SCALE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 872526.

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PROJECT INFORMATION

TITLE	RRI2SCALE – Responsible Research and Innovation Ecosystems at Regional Scale for Intelligent Cities, Transport and Energy
START DATE	1 January 2020
DURATION	36 months
WEBSITE	https://rri2scale.eu/
COORDINATOR	AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA - Italy
PROJECT OVERVIEW	RRI2SCALE has designed a robust methodological approach to assist regional R&I governance systems to effectively and sustainably address their Regional Dilemmas. Techno-moral scenarios will be “tested” via JRC’s Scenario Exploration System and Regional Dialogues, forming the basis for elaborating Regional Agendas and Roadmaps towards the integration of RRI principles into territorial R&I design. All project results will form the RRI2SCALE Toolkit for replication by other territories.
CONSORTIUM	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA https://www.apre.it/ 2. HOGSKULEN PA VESTLANDET https://www.hvl.no/ 3. UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/ 4. UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE https://www.utwente.nl/en/ 5. Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC https://qplan-intl.gr/ 6. RESEARCH AND INNOVATION MANAGEMENT GMBH https://www.research-and-innovation-management.com/ 7. WHITE RESEARCH SPRL https://white-research.eu/ 8. HORDALAND FYLKESKOMMUNE https://www.hordaland.no/ 9. PROVINCIE OVERIJSEL https://www.overijssel.nl/ 10. KRITI https://www.crete.gov.gr/ 11. AXENCIA GALEGA DE INNOVACION http://gain.xunta.gal/

The present document provides a questionnaire that local or regional authorities can use to run a Delphi study on smart cities, transport and energy.

Clicking on the “I consent” button indicates that:

- You have read and understood the invitation e-mail sent to you and the purpose of this forward-looking exercise.
- You consent to your personal data being securely stored and retained for 1 year after the completion of the study, before ultimately being deleted by the consortium that collected this data.
- You consent to your personal data being processed by the online survey development software ‘Welphi’ based on the company’s privacy policy.
- You consent to anonymized quotations from your answers to be used in reports, publications, and publicly available outputs (e.g., infographics, etc.) of the study.
- You understand that you are free to withdraw your consent at any time without the need to justify your decision.
- You confirm that you have read and understood all the above and been given adequate time to consider your participation.

I consent

1. Based on your academic and/or professional background, how would you rate your level of expertise in the following fields?

Field	High	Moderate	Low	None
intelligent cities (e.g., data-driven governance)				
intelligent energy (e.g., smart grid, energy communities)				
intelligent transport (e.g., Intelligent Transport Systems)				
digital technologies and their societal impacts in general				
Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)				

2. You participate in this survey as member of:

- academia or research
- governmental body
- business
- civil society organization
- other (please specify)

3. Which is your country of residence?

[drop-down menu with all the EU-27 countries + “other” option and open box to indicate which “other” country they mean]

4. Are you based in any of the following European Regions?

- Vestland (Norway)
- Overijssel (the Netherlands)
- Kriti (Greece)
- Galicia (Spain)
- None of the above

Please state the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements in a time horizon of 10 years from today.

	Firmly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Firmly Agree
1. The need to address growing urban challenges (e.g. increasing housing prices, traffic congestion, poor air quality, and urban flooding) will be one of the key drivers for European cities to pursue smart city projects (in the areas of governance, energy, transport, health, etc.) in the next decade.					
2. Territorial phenomena that jeopardize environmental, social and economic sustainability (e.g., urban sprawl, overurbanization and uncontrolled urban development) will be the key driver for European cities to pursue smart city projects (in the areas of governance, energy, transport, health, etc.).					
3. Policymakers at both European and national level will support the design and implementation of local smart city initiatives through relevant policies and funding schemes.					
4. The technological advancements that will happen in areas such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) will improve the efficiency of smart city projects, making the prospect of smart city development even more attractive to European cities.					
5. Local policymakers in Europe will design innovation strategies that are more citizen-centric, rather than technology-driven and hence, they will prioritize initiatives that focus on the needs and preferences of citizens.					
6. Citizens in Europe will be increasingly motivated to co-design and co-implement intelligent city solutions and participate in public discussions about their deployment in their city.					
7. Local policymakers in Europe will adopt an entrepreneurial mindset when designing smart city programs and services (i.e. specify the services' value proposition, use smart procurement models and attribute importance to sustainability beyond funding).					
8. In their quest to adopt more financially viable and sustainable business models for their smart city projects, many European cities will encourage investment from the private sector.					
9. The outsourcing of smart city services and the adoption of business-like practices by European local administrations will undermine the importance of social and environmental benefits for society, in favor of economic benefits and efficiency gains.					
10. The market of technology vendors in the smart city domain will become highly concentrated by 2030, restricting the bargaining power of European cities and resulting to 'technology lock-in' phenomena.					
11. Ethical concerns associated with the use of intelligent technologies (e.g. the "moral values" of self-driving cars) will					

grow in importance and urgency in Europe and will drive the smart city solutions market.					
12. Privacy, security, safety, and ethical concerns will increase the reluctance of citizens to adopt new technologies, slowing down the uptake and proliferation of intelligent city initiatives.					
13. European regulatory frameworks will adapt to regulate privacy, security, safety, and ethical issues that arise due to the advent of intelligent technologies. Yet, national regulatory frameworks will adapt to these at an unequal pace across all EU-27 countries.					
14. Intelligent city initiatives that will be undertaken in Europe will be designed in ways that consider the needs of vulnerable groups (such as the elderly and people with disabilities) improving the prospect to contribute to social inclusion significantly. Yet, these initiatives will be unequally uptaken across European countries.					
15. Due to the deployment of intelligent city initiatives, socio-spatial segregation within European cities within the next decade will increase. More specifically, quality of life in certain urbanized areas will improve thanks to new technologies; in sequence, the cost of housing will rise; eventually lower-income populations will be displaced to other parts of the cities (the so-called "gentrification" phenomenon).					
16. Intelligent technologies within the next decade will have a negative net impact on employment in Europe, due to automation and large adoption/promotion of the gig economy (the so-called "uberisation").					

Please state the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements in a time horizon of 10 years from today.

	Firmly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Firmly Agree
1. Public transport authorities and operators in Europe will mainly use intelligent technologies to develop more cost-effective solutions for the delivery of public transport services.					
2. The number of either semi- or fully autonomous vehicles by 2030 will not increase significantly in Europe, due to public concerns regarding their safety.					
3. Intelligent technologies will be transforming travel via public means of transport (bus, trains) from "waste" travel time to "bonus" time in Europe. For instance, thanks to high-speed and seamless wireless connectivity, commuters will have the opportunity to work during their commuting time.					
4. The expansion of seamless connectivity and interoperability in digital services in European cities will further promote shared mobility solutions (e.g., ridesharing, carsharing and bike-sharing).					
5. The expansion of seamless connectivity and interoperability in digital services in European cities will urge the evolution of micro mobility (e.g. bicycles, scooters, electric skateboards).					

6. The adoption of intelligent transport solutions will sharpen regional inequalities, as advanced regions with the necessary resources (infrastructures, financial capacity, etc.) will outpace the less developed ones.					
7. The use of Big Data and Artificial Intelligence (AI) will significantly contribute in the development and uptake of interconnected on-demand public transport in the next decade at regional level, also improving the connectivity between urban and rural areas across Europe.					

Please state the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements in a time horizon of 10 years from today.

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Please state the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements in a time horizon of 10 years from today.

	Firmly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Firmly Agree
1. The energy system transition will be pursued mainly by adapting and repurposing existing organizations and infrastructures and not replacing them with new ones. To this end, intelligent technologies will be introduced in the energy					

domain without fundamentally disrupting or rescaling system operation and ownership.					
2. Digitalization and smaller-scale generation and storage will drive a rescaling and decentralization of the system, both technically and institutionally, with regional and city/local authorities becoming key energy strategists.					
3. By 2030 the number of energy prosumers (i.e. individuals that both produce and consume energy) will significantly increase in Europe.					
4. The number of energy communities (i.e. communities that engage in collective energy actions guided by open and democratic participation and governance) will significantly increase in Europe.					
5. The adoption of intelligent energy solutions in Europe will significantly decrease the cost of electricity for households and businesses.					
6. Currently, the existing grid and the existing fossil fuel system are used to back up supply when energy from renewables is not available. This will continue being the norm in the next decade.					
7. Energy consumption can be expected to fall in the coming decade, due to remote working and digitized business operations, supported by sustained energy conservation measures.					
8. The need to analyze demand and adjust how much power is drawn and from where across the distributed grids will drive the advancement of intelligent technologies such as predictive AI, machine learning, IoT and blockchain.					